

MEMORANDUM

FROM: O [REDACTED] K [REDACTED] A [REDACTED]

TO: THE CLERK, CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL
AFFAIRS, PARLIAMENT HOUSE, ACCRA

SUBJECT: THE NEED TO CRIMINALIZE LBGTQ+ AND
OTHER HOMOSEXUAL TENDENCIES IN GHANA

DATE: 6TH October, 2021

This memorandum is to support the bill currently in Parliament proscribing LGBT+ and other homosexual activities and tendencies in Ghana.

The *locus classicus* of what constitutes marriage is Genesis 2:18. This reads:

The LORD God said, "It is not good for the man to be alone. I will make a helper suitable for him."

And Genesis 2:24:

"That is why a man leaves his father and mother and is united to his wife and they become one flesh".

Lord Penzance defined marriage in the case of *Hyde V Hyde* thus:

"I conceive that marriage, as understood may for this

purpose be defined as the **voluntary union for life of one man and one woman to the exclusion of all others**".

This definition of marriage is of interest to us as Ghanaians, in that it defines marriage as a union of a biological man and a biological woman. This means that LBGTQ+ and other homosexual tendencies are precluded and proscribed in Ghana.

Moreover, all ethnic groups, cultures and all forms of marriages in Ghana do not permit a union or relationship between a man and another man; nor between a woman and another woman. In Ghana homosexuality is illegal and a taboo. It is proscribed under the Laws of Ghana. Section 104 of the Criminal Offences Act, 1960 (Act 29) makes homosexuality an offence punishable by imprisonment.

Section 104 reads:

Unnatural Carnal Knowledge

1. A person who has unnatural carnal knowledge
 - a. Of another person of not less than sixteen years of age without the consent of that person commits a first degree felony and is liable on conviction to a term of imprisonment of not less than five years and not more than twenty-five years; or
 - b. Of another person of not less than sixteen years of age with the consent of that other person commits a misdemeanour; or
 - c. Of an animal commits a misdemeanour.

2. Unnatural carnal knowledge is sexual intercourse with a person in an unnatural manner or, with an animal.

The Lord Jesus in Matthew 19: 4–6 corroborates the account of marriage as between a man and a woman in Genesis 2: 24 thus:

“Haven’t you read”, He replied, “that at the beginning the Creator made them male and female, and said,

“For this reason a man will leave his father and mother and be united to his wife, and the two will become one flesh?”

“So they are no longer two, but one flesh. Therefore what God has joined together, let no one separate” (NIV).

Christ Jesus in answering a question posed to Him by the Pharisees about marriage posited that in the beginning of creation marriage was the union between a male and a female. This goes against postmodern teachings that seek to legalize the union of a man and another man; or a woman and another woman. Have ye not read that He Who made them at the beginning made them male and female? This closes all arguments and debates that tend to justify LBGTQ+ and homosexuality.

In Romans chapter one, Apostle Paul also condemned homosexuality as being evil and ungodly.